

Leadership Performance and Corporate Quality Culture in Strategic Organizations: The EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model for Armed Forces

Ramazan ERTURGUT¹, Serhat SOYSEKERCI²

¹ Assoc. Prof. Dr. University of South Florida, Tampa, FL, U.S.

² Assis. Prof. Dr. Canakkale 18 March University, Canakkale, Turkey.

Abstract

In today's world, which is referred to as a global village, the competition of national and International organizations is increasing and it has become an obligation for organizations of all scales to manufacture quality goods and to give quality service. Organizational culture is a guideline potential of the employees, managers and the behaviours and beliefs of the organization as a whole. It is evaluated that without the active participation and creative power of the employees within strategic public bodies such as the Armed Forces, institutionalization of quality efforts will not be possible. In this study, the EFQM (European Foundation for Quality Management) Excellence Model and the Transformational Leadership Model, which is a postmodern leadership model, is synthesized and presented as the "EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model" in order to increase employee performance and institutionalize quality culture in the Armed Forces. In this context, a theoretical analysis of EFQM Excellence Model and Transformational Leadership has been scoped out. In the following section, the EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model which consists of the sixteen steps of Transformational Leadership and the expected results of the model in the creation of a quality organization for the efficiency and performance in the Armed Forces is proposed.

Keywords: Leadership; Quality Culture; Strategic Organization; Military Leadership, TQM, EFQM.

Note: First version of this article was presented in NATO Research and Technology Symposium, by NATO SAS-073 Organization, Brussels, Belgium, March 2009.

1. Introduction

In today's technological environment; the humanity is aware of rapid change that seems to affect every area. These wide ranges of changes in environmental conditions that the organizations take place have increased the importance of relations between managers, employees and organizational structure.

In worldwide, in strategic corporations like armed forces, creation and sharing of information have become faster in an important manner because of communication technologies. This situation perpetually forces every defend organization to change and to get ready of probable crisis and opportunities because of change. The commanders and managers who have the "being ready" responsibility should not only be flexible to change but also should have management culture and executive talent to perform change, and these parameters form distinguishing features. Today, a leading approach that will give the needed acceleration to national and international defend organizations

¹*Assoc. Prof. Dr., Ramazan ERTURGUT has been supported by TUBITAK (The Scientific and Technical Research Council of Turkey) during this study.

is evaluated as transformational leadership, depends on a leader who transforms followers and transforms itself in this process. [1]

2. Aim of Research

The aim of this study is, in world armed forces, to open a negotiation over human resources performance and to present a model suggestion about both EFQM (European Foundation for Quality Management) Excellence Model which is an important criterion in evaluation of corporate quality, and transformational leadership behaviors which are postmodern leadership approaches.

3. Transformational Leadership Concept

Transformational leadership was brought up to negotiation by Bernard Bass. He introduced transformational leadership as the leadership that has great effects over followers to literature. According to Bass, transformational leaders should induce awareness to the juniors about the importance of performing their mission in high performance, and persuade juniors about covering high level needs. This is only possible with reaching corporate goals, so they change and motivate followers. Therefore, the followers of transformational leaders trust them, believe them and respect them.[2]

Gary Yukl defined transformational leadership as “the period in which creation of loyalty to the goals of organization and providing the followers with necessary power in reaching these goals are performed.”[3] While Leitwood states that transformational leadership is “resetting of people’s visions and missions, refreshing responsibilities and reorganizing process in order to reach goals,”[4] İşcan, asserts that transformational leaders are people who are defined by employees as “the leader that have important effect in our business and personal life.”[5] Transformational leadership is defined by Herriegel, J.W. Slocum and Woodman as “the usage of charismatic talent with the power of attention and personality, capturing the attention of followers, and the process of high level motivation.”[6] The conceptual frame of transformational leadership is as follows:[7]

Fig 1: Conceptual Frame of Transformational Leadership

Behavioral dimensions of transformational leadership are known as Intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, Individualized consideration and idealized effect.[8] Other properties of this type of leadership in literature are creation and sharing of common vision, mental sensation and creativity, charismatic power, ability of high level communication and motivation, leader of transformation, emotional power and bravery and risk based approach, being trustworthy and self-esteem. [9]

4. EFQM Excellence Model and Corporate Analysis

Quality prizes organizations symbolize prestige and excellence not only for the private but for the public sector as well due to the fact that it measures the integrated management system in all its facets (not just one), and all its processes, targets and its competitive position in the market. In the accepted sense there are three global quality awards. These are the Malcolm Baldrige quality prize in the USA, The Deming quality prize in Japan the EFQM

quality prize given in Europe. Like most of European countries, in Turkey many institutions in the public or the private domain start their TQM applications by taking the “Excellence Model” developed by the European Quality Management Foundation (EFQM) as their basis and start with self evaluation processes and this is continued in line with the plan developed as a result of the self evaluation work to improve the specified corporate areas. Today many corporations/institutions have achieved results that can be considered as exemplary that can be shown as an example to many corporations/institutions. EFQM Excellence Model given in Figure, 2. [10]

Fig 2: The EFQM Excellence Model

EFQM Excellence Model is a model based on nine main criteria. Five of these criteria are “inputs” and four represent the result criteria. The input criteria represent the operations of an institution. The result criteria represent what that institution has realized. The results are a consequence of the inputs. The model that has been designed to take into the account that there may be many approaches in order achieve sustainable excellence in all dimensions related to performance can be summarized by the following sentence. The excellence of results that are experienced by the customers, personnel, and the community in terms of performance, can be provided by the management of the policy, and strategy, the personnel, resources, guided by an appropriate leadership philosophy and understanding . [11]

The nine boxes shown in Figure 2 represent the main criteria that contain the evaluation of the efforts made by the institution in trying to achieve excellence. There are detailed sub descriptions of each criterion that outline it in detail. Each criterion has been supported by numbers of sub criteria in order to make it easier to understand. The sub criteria contain many questions that need to be answered in the process of evaluation. Last of all, in all six criteria, there is a list of related fields. The related field lists are not fixed or compulsory. But they are of assistance in explaining the sub criteria by means of sub articles.

5. EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model

In world armed forces, the process of adaptation to EFQM model applications and organizational transformation require the high attention from top management. Therefore, quality applications require more transformational leadership features than classical leadership features. In order to apply EFQM Excellence Model continuously and effectively to armed forces organizations, it is needed to apply some steps in a hierarchical manner.[12] In the table below, the process of introduction to EFQM Model is given with transformational leadership steps.

Fig 3: EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model

5.1. Awareness in the Need of Change

The main theme of EFQM Based Transformational Leadership Model is organizational transformation and need of new culture creation. One of other main properties of transformational leadership is that transformational leadership has a structure that can perceive the need of change.[13] According to Drucker, the leader of change is always ready for action.[14] When evaluating the defense concept as a function of change, it will be understood that the leader's perception and management of change ability is of great importance. Armed forces, due to the attributed mission quality, take the responsibility of immediate action taking and respond to crisis.

5.2. Adaption of Philosophy by the Leader

The main difference of armed forces with a factory organization is that the employees of armed forces have emotional integrity. Thus, the properties of work done increase the expected sacrifice level. Therefore, one cannot oversee the motivational factors in human resources which have important effects for managing the military operations. According to some specialists, EFQM Model is the approach of "taking the employees seriously." The importance of EFQM applications role in the process of change will be understood by the manager/commander.

5.3. Decision of Applying EFQM Model

It starts with a strategical decision that is taken and supported by top management. The member of top management who wants to apply EFQM philosophy in a military organization, should prioritize the determination of the resource and its reason. He has to make a decision in accordance with the processes of co-departments and organizational environment in armed forces, along with the fact that EFQM is a new trend philosophy that has been applied to public sector for 20 years.[15]

The kick-off meetings in which the decision of adaptation to EFQM model is declared to junior levels are very important.[11] The leader should care about the start-up speech as much as the expected resistances from other sides.[17] Therefore, the member of the top management should attend the kick-off meeting in person in which the introduction to EFQM applications will be declared and should make a speech.[14] In transformational leadership, effective behaviors of the leader are explained through "idealized effect" behaviors and it is known that transformational leaders are successful speakers. The speech of transformational leaders effects vast groups. In this level, the style and the level of persuasion of the member of top management who embodies the qualities of transformational leadership are of major importance.

5.4. Motivate and Believe Followers for Change

According to EFQM Model, intelligence and leadership talent of a person who is the head of organization is not enough. In military organizations, the experience and talent of all staff from core military unit to complete army are very important.[16] The attention of staff is relative to communication channels between staff and departments in the organization. Moreover, motivating staff to teamwork and helping each other is of utmost importance. In organizations that EFQM applications exist non-hierarchical and trustable behaviors of transformational leaders increase the loyalty of junior staff because of emotional effect [7]. In this step, coordinating individuals with group and motivating them to teamwork is the agenda of the transformational leader[15].

5.5. Establishing Transformation Consciousness and Belief in Followers

In introduction to EFQM application process, employees should understand the change, be convinced about the requirements of quality applications and be attentive to change process. In this process of change, firstly, manager/commander should convince the junior staff about the necessity of change, then use the motivation power over followers in order to convince them about the benefits of change. In transformational leadership, leadership behaviours that cause motivation cover “inspirational motivation” dimension. In hierarchical organizations, it is concrete that convincing employees for marginal changes cannot be performed with traditional behaviours. In this step, in order to convince and motivate followers, transformational leaders should get individual risk and behave in an untraditional way in order to get trust.

5.6. Analysis of Organizational Culture

This step contains collecting information about organizational culture and investigating the current status in armed forces. Motives (such as routines, traditions, beliefs, behaviours, morals and ethics) that are authorized to organizations should be analysed by the leader. As a result of a research about the role of organizational culture in TQM applications (USA, 1994), the establishment and development of TQM needs culture that contains at about seven years. According to research, the most important role in accomplishment of transformation process is the support of the human resources that bases, applies and projects the results of human and human oriented applications.[17] Investigation of organizational culture requires that transformational leader should know gathering information behaviours of followers, formal and informal relationships that effect the processes of organization. Moreover, transformational leader has to know the level of open-mindedness organization in order to warn the followers intellectually.

5.7. Creating Vision, Determining Mission and Developing Strategy

Drawing an exciting vision picture to employees will be enforcing power in EFQM applications. Such as being the fastest mission power in the world, being the most powerful air force in own geo-strategical area, and etc.

The mission is a list of job description, service area, production gap of the product and the services, and the description of how to get them ready. According to EFQM philosophy, mission of an organization focuses on customer satisfaction, so customer satisfaction will enable the continuity of the organization.[20] In armed forces, internal customer is personnel, external customer is a citizen who demands a defensive service. The leader/commander who has transformational ability, will reconsider the problems and the causes of the problems that are relevant to the mission of the organization. Hence, the squat that will take part in the operations will affect the overall success of the group, if the problems are not solved during a peaceful period.

When creating the right strategy to EFQM Model, it is aimed to transform organizational structure from hierarchical relations to horizontal organizational structure. In general military conjuctor, changes in competitors and technology and employees' behaviors to these changes are very important parameters over accomplishment and failure of organizations that supply defensive service. Therefore, this can only be done with strategical planning.

Leader should link vision, mission and strategy to each other in his speech. Goldberg asserts the importance of linking every message that are relevant with strategies and tactics to vision and mission sentences for the leader.[24] Moreover, understanding the mission sentences of the organization clearly will enable the leader to select appropriate strategy for the purpose of the organization and to apply them.[21]

In an organization that is prepared to EFQM applications, “idealized effect” behaviors, based on charisma such as “taking pride, trusting and gaining respect” that are assigned to transformational leader, and leader’s “creating vision and determining mission” “idealizing effects behaviors will be effective. Helping employees for development of dreams and talents and creating vision for organization are fundamental factors of transformational leadership.[21]

5.8. Determining EFQM Policy

Quality policy at organizations has been declared since 1980's.[12] Drucker points that an entrepreneur that wants to be successful change leader, must have a policy about systematic innovations.[13] According to the result of the research that was performed by ASQC/Gallup, the responsibility of determining quality policy does not belong to a board of directors, but it belongs to top management.[14] Members of the top management and other managers have to evaluate the importance of subjects about applications in order to create the structure of the policy. In addition, top management should pay attention covering EFQM policy from managers to security personnel. In world armed forces, the existence of clearly defined quality policies is important over career planning of human resources.

5.9. Introduction to EFQM Model and Management of Introduction

Herriegel and Slocum stressed that, one of transformational leadership base is "management of effects"[6]. Without a doubt; an introduction to EFQM model will affect the structure of armed forces, processes and individuals. At that point, transformational leader/commander should support the staff and pay more attention to individuals and departments that are affected by introduction process. The leader's behaviours' which will cause psychological relief will refresh the employee's self-esteem. Applications which require new and rapid change cause a resist in every organization. In the organization of the armed forces, vertical and horizontal relations are clearly set, moreover, authorizations and responsibilities are clearly defined. Because of set working conditions and authority in armed forces, the introduction process will be faster and easy compared to other organizations.

5.10. Management of Resist to Change

Generally, people resist changing. Drucker asserts "Innovation set aside, doing something different also causes unexpected hills. Therefore, in order to change something, a leader who has proven his talents is needed"[13]. One of the most important aspects of the transformational leaders is that they should successfully manage the resistance against change. Buhler states that transformational leaders are patient, hardworking and persistent. Therefore, when they face resistance, they make a long term decision that will supply benefit to organization instead of short term decisions [22]. In armed forces, in order to break resistance to change, it will be beneficial for the leader to persuade the juniors about the necessity of new ideas and applications both for top management and themselves [23]. These behaviors cover the "inspirational motivation" behavioral aspect of the commander.

5.11. Using Quality Application Techniques

Top management should supply financial fund for employees in order to learn quality application techniques [24]. In this step, it is expected from the leaders to use TQM techniques and suggestions which are produced after group works to analyze the data obtained from table, histogram and pareto analysis immediately, and use in processes that are relevant to product and service production. In TQM techniques application process, the commander who has transformational behaviors can provide personal and intellectual support. In armed forces, personnel turnover rate is high and human resources are geographically replaced in a perpetual manner. Therefore, using and saving numeral techniques in work processes is important in the continuity of corporate benefits.

5.12. Development of Personnel and Citizen Satisfaction

It could be observed that throughout history, dramatic military success stories embody motivational leadership talents. Therefore, it could be stated that the leadership qualities which are required by the armed forces are the qualities of transformational leadership. Considering the fact that in strategical public organizations, the main aim of the quality management is to reduce the cost and increase quality of the service and production, it is quite obvious that this aim requires workers with high maintenance. The type of leadership which transforms its audience into individuals of high maintenance is transformational leadership. In armed forces which provide the country with national guarding service, providing satisfaction of the citizens and human resources, and efficiency could be the leading path to national peace and its maintenance.

5.13. Developing Peace in Publicity

One of the expected results of the EFQM Model is providing and maintaining public peace. The armed forces of the countries provide the countries with a national guarding service and this service is considered to be of public service. The high level of satisfaction of society who receive this service could be the key to a peaceful state between the state and its citizens and national peace.

5.14. Empowering the Employees through Education and Authorization

In armed forces, the leaders should consider the individual as the most important gain, and with this thought in mind, they should not avoid investment to this means.[25] The tagline of the EFQM model is "renewed education, improved education." This education is given to all staff, for each personnel, on every needed subject, and throughout the application. Education is also needed to change the routine of non-productive work processes and

the culture of the past. Schermerhorn has stated that one of the aspects of transformational leadership is authorization and strengthening.[26] In addition, transformational leadership should also include “individual support” so that the staff works efficiently and receives sufficient education for personal development. In military structures, transformational leaders may use management information systems as a means of avoiding confusion in authorization turnover.[11]

5.15. Creating New Organizational Culture

In organizations where EFQM applications are executed, all these steps in transformational leadership will lead to a new social structure. At this level, transformational leadership should keep the facts within the organization in mind, and reform a new social structure through the renewal in the organization.[27] According to Yukl, when transformational leaders are reforming a new social structure through the renewal in the organization, they get rid of running over authorization, unnecessary bureaucratic arrangements and help the staff increase their training and talents.[6]

The most suitable organizational structure for both organizational structures required by TQM applications and transformational leadership qualities leads to a horizontal and a flexible one. A horizontal structure raises the quality applications and makes the communication easier by decreasing the hierarchical structure, and thus increases the tendency towards a participatory and a collaborative structure avoiding the harsh quality of hierarchy.[3] Armed forces, this quality outshines the “full authority” structure and this model supports a participatory frame and forms an organizational unity.

5.16. Institutionalizing the Organizational Culture and Forming an Organizational Unity

According to Tichy and Sherman, as the last step of transformational leadership, the changes in the organization, renewed behavioral, productive and management changes should be institutionalized.[12] However, a dynamic change should be reinforced instead of a static one. In order to institutionalize the organizational structure formed by TQM, the vision and the commitment of the top management should be continuously given to all staff. The assets and beliefs of the leaders help the institutionalizing the organizational vision and fulfilling organizational aims.[21] The leader who embodies the transformational qualities should put forward the assets which could be adopted by all staff. The new qualities, facilities and applications should be shared by every individual in the organization. The changes in communication, decision making and problem solving systems will be the means in the sharing of the change and thus reaching the organizational vision will be easier.[18] The institutionalizing of the change in the organizations which benefit from TQM applications requires refreshment and reshaping the newly gained cultural reformations.

6. Conclusion

Applications of EFQM Excellence Model are evaluated as important value conversions and leading transformational values in world armed forces. Some of the citizens think that national and international security service concepts are important in the government sector, because in world armed forces, quality means not only having aversive gun systems or not to head of army in owned geostrategic territory, in addition, it contains social peace and missed global peace concepts.

In some countries, EFQM applications from army to schools are used like government reform by success oriented government organizations. In army forces, EFQM Model and managerial applications are considered as the base of change in a positive way. When leadership capability is considered as a very important concept in army forces, EFQM based transformational leadership approximation can be the development and the changing tool for world army forces evaluation. In total, EFQM based converter leadership applications is considered to be the key of increasing human resources performance and results of achieving citizen satisfaction and also social peace. It is necessary accommodating critical factors of army organizations and fundamentals of EFQM Models and characteristics of transformational leadership. In addition to this, it was proved that leadership is developed by learnable behaviors more than by birth abilities. According to Hase, transformational leadership capability can be taught and developed first in military schools and then barracks. It is regarded that the internal training is the core and the means which serve for the benefit of achieving this goal.

References

- [1] Çakar U. & Arbak, Y. (2003) “Is it Necessary Emotional Intelligence for Transformational Leadership? An Empirical Study on Managers” *Journal of Economic & Administration Sciences D.E.U. Publish* , 18-2, p.84.
- [2] Bass, B.M. (1990) “From Transactional to Transformational Leadership: Learning to Share The Vision”, *Organizational Dynamics*, 19(3), p.21.
- [3] Özalp, İ. (2000) *Businnes Adminisration* , A.U. Publish, Eskişehir, Turkey, p.346

- [4] Leitwood K. D., & Genge, M. (1996) *Transformational Leadership* International Handbook of Educational Leadership and Administration, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Netherlands, p.839.
- [5] İřcan, Ö.F. (2006). “Perception of Transformational and Transactional Leadership & It’s Role of Organizational Purification”, *Akdeniz University Journal of Economic & Administration Sciences* 4 (2), p.164.
- [6] Erçetin, ř. (2000). *Vision in Leader Spiral* , Ankara, Nobel Publishing, p.6
- [7] Herriegel, D. & Woodman, R.W. (1995). *Organizational Behavior* West Publishing Company p. 378
- [8] Bass, B. M. (1998). *Transformational leadership: Industrial, military, and educational impact*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- [9] <http://www.efqm.org/>, 24 August 2015.
- [10] Saatçiođlu, Ö. (2006). *Excellence Models at University Administration and Evaluations Scales for Rector Candidates* [http:// www.odtu.edu.tr. oed/index2.php](http://www.odtu.edu.tr/oed/index2.php).
- [11] Ardiç, K. (2006). *Leadership Peaces in Total Quality*, <http://www.bilgiyönetimi.org>.
- [12] Çetin, C. (2007). *Individual Quality*, <http://www.canancetin.com>.
- [13] Drucker, P.F. (1999). *Management Arguments for 21'th. Century*, Trans. By Bahçivangil, İ& Garbon, G. Epsilon Publishing Company, p.86.
- [14] Kovancı, A. (2001). *Total Quality Management But How?* İstanbul Sistem Publishing, p.27.
- [15] Çetin, C. (2002). *Consultations Methods*, Beta Publishing, İstanbul, p.154.
- [16] Genç, N.&Halis, M. (2006). *Quality Leadership*, Timas Publishing Company, Istanbul, Turkey.
- [17] Erdoğan, G.T. (2004). *Effect of Total Quality Management on Human Resource and Job Satisfaction a Local Study*” D.E.Unv. Published Ph-D Thesis.
- [18] Total Quality Management Handbook <http://www.kalitekontrol.org.tr>, May 2006.
- [19] Dođan, E. (2002). *Employee Job Attracting: Transformational leadership Style, Trusting to Leader , Empowerment and Intelligence Effects*, Published Ph-D Thesis, Marmara University SSI, p.118
- [20] Altuđ, D. (1997). *Organizational Behaviour*, Haberal Educational Cognizant, Ankara, p.47.
- [21] Çelik, V. (1998). “Transformational Leadership in Education”, *Journal of Educational Management*, Ankara, p. 426.
- [22] Buhler, P. (1995). “Leaders vs. Managers”, *Supervision*, 56(4), 107-114.
- [23] Hodgetts, R.M. (1997). *Management: Theory, Process&Application*, Trans. by Çetin, C. Der Publishing, p. 269.
- [24] Balcı, A. (2002). *Implementation of Total Quality Management in Public Sector: An Empirical Analysis of a Turkish Case*, (Published Ph-D Thesis, METU SSI. p.255.
- [25] Efil, İ. (1995). *An Important vehicle for achieving Total Quality ISO 9000 Quality System* Uludađ Unv. Publish, p.16.
- [26] Schermerhorn, J.R. (1996). *Management And Organizational Behavior Essentials*, John Wiley&Sons Inc., p.109.
- [27] Caudron, S. (1993). *How HR Drives TQM*, Personel Journal, p. 48-.51.
- [28] Tichy N.M. & Ulrich, D. (1984). *SMR Forum: The Leadership Challenge A-Call For The Transformational Leader*, *Sloan Management Review*, Fall, p.72.